

Horizon 2020 ULTRAWAVE

Ultra capacity wireless layer beyond 100 GHz based on millimeter wave Traveling Wave Tubes

WP7. Deliverable D7.1: Press Release

Start date of project: 01.09.2017

Duration: 36 months

Project no: 762119

Project acronym: **ULTRAWAVE**

Organisation name of lead contractor for this report: Universitat Politecnica de Valencia, Spain

Dissemination level

PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Dissemination to general public and scientific community are priorities for the ULTRAWAVE consortium. The first press release is written in a language accessible to the general public, but with the intention to stimulate the interest of the scientific community. The interest in the project is demonstrated by the propagation of the press release in press, science and tech websites.

This deliverable contains a report on the first press release launched by Lancaster University on the 12 September 2017 and how it has been disseminated. Additionally, other actions taken by other partners to advertise the project are reported.

The press release can be read in Annex I. The press release press release developed by UPV press office is in Annex II. Examples of the ULTRAWAVE press release publication in a variety of electronic media are given in Annex III.

1. INTRODUCTION

ULTRAWAVE responds to the challenge of high capacity, high cell density backhaul by proposing, for the first time, the exploitation of the whole millimeter wave spectrum beyond 100 GHz. This will be used to create an ultra-capacity layer providing more than 100 Gbps/km² in Point to Multi point at D-band (141 – 174.8 GHz) over 500 m radius of coverage, fed by novel G-band (300 GHz) Point to Point high capacity links with more than 600 m range.

The ULTRAWAVE system is empowered by the convergence of three main technologies: vacuum electronics, solid-state electronics and photonics in a unique wireless system, with transmission power at Watt level at millimeter waves, generated by novel traveling wave tubes. The vast capacity, flexibility and easy deployment of the ULTRAWAVE layer will enable backhaul of hundreds of small and pico cells, no matter the density, and will open scenarios for new networks paradigms and architectures aiming at a full 5G implementation.

In order to ensure that the ULTRAWAVE project and its innovative approach are successfully promoted to its target audience, the dissemination and communication activities are of great importance for the project partners. The main target audience of the dissemination activities is industry, technical and scientific audience, potential End Users such as telecom operators, interested public and standardization bodies working on the millimeter bands and on definition of Multimedia Wireless Systems (MWS). Moreover, since the European Society as a whole will ultimately benefit from the results of the project (in terms of offering broadband access and new services with high added value such as e-learning, e-health, etc.), special measures will be planned to reach the wide public.

As a first dissemination activity, a press release has been launched by Lancaster University as a first step to trigger interest of professional and the society in general for research activities performed in ULTRAWAVE.

2. PRESS RELEASE

A first press release announcing the ULTRAWAVE project was produced by Lancaster University to officially launch the project and to make publicity of the kick-off meeting, which was held in Lancaster on the 14th and 15th of September, 2017.

This press release was posted on the News of the Lancaster University website (Fig.1) and has been distributed among general press magazines and other media, as explained in Section 3.

The following link gives access to the press release, which is also attached in Annex I.

<http://www.lancaster.ac.uk/engineering/news-and-events/news/2017/september17/engineers-to-pioneer-unprecedented-high-speed-wireless-data-coverage-/>

Fig. 1. ULTRAWAVE press release posted on the News section of Lancaster University website

UPV has distributed a press release among several Spanish media. This press release (in Spanish) is enclosed in the Annex II. A webpage on ULTRAWAVE is available on the UPV website:

<https://www.ntc.upv.es/proyectos/ultrawave.html>

GUF has released a press release in Germany

<http://aktuelles.uni-frankfurt.de/forschung/ultrawave-schnellere-datenuebertragung-fuer-mobile-endgeraete/>

LU announced the kick-off meeting in News Section September 6th with by using the Eventbrite portal.

<https://www.eventbrite.co.uk/e/ultrawave-wireless-communications-toward-the-300-ghz-the-kick-off-workshop-tickets-36562204538?aff=es2>

In addition to the actions listed above, other ULTRAWAVE partners have planned to deliver press releases.

3. PUBLICATION CHANNELS

The ULTRAWAVE press release posted on the website of the Lancaster University and UPV has been published by communication agencies and several electronic media listed below:

- **My Science UK** (<https://www.myscience.org.uk/>)

Engineers to pioneer unprecedented high-speed wireless data coverage

MyScience (Web), 6/09/2017, Unattributed

The ULTRAWAVE programme will develop ubiquitous wireless data coverage with unprecedented speed at millimetre waves

Link to the news:

https://www.myscience.org.uk/wire/engineers_to_pioneer_unprecedented_high_speed_wireless_data_coverage-2017-lancaster

- **The Engineer** (<http://www.theengineer.co.uk/>) (41000 readers)

W-band wireless broadband system aims to streamline services

The Engineer (Web), 19/09/2017, Helen Knight

Ubiquitous 5G wireless data coverage with speeds of up to 100 gigabits per second could be made possible by a European project developing technologies to exploit the millimetre wave spectrum..

Link to the news: <https://www.theengineer.co.uk/pioneer-high-speed-wireless-data-coverage/>

- **Technology.org** (<https://www.technology.org/>)

Engineers to pioneer unprecedented high speed wireless data coverage

Technology.org (Web), 7/09/2017, Unattributed

A major new international research programme is responding to the overwhelming demand of internet traffic to develop ubiquitous wireless data coverage with unprecedented speed at millimetre waves.

Link to the news: <https://www.technology.org/2017/09/07/engineers-to-pioneer-unprecedented-high-speed-wireless-data-coverage/>

- **World Industrial Reporter** (<https://worldindustrialreporter.com/>)

EU Project Exploits Millimeter Wave Spectrum to Advance 5G Speed, Coverage

World Industrial Reporter (Web), 21/09/2017, Aruna Urs

ULTRAWAVE, the \$3.4 million European Union Horizon 2020 project, hopes to make 5G wireless data coverage universal, with speeds of up to 100 gigabits per second.

Link to the news: <https://worldindustrialreporter.com/eu-project-exploits-millimeter-wave-spectrum-to-advance-5g-speed-coverage/>

- **La Vanguardia** (<http://www.lavanguardia.com/>)

European project looks for efficient high speed wireless connections

La Vanguardia (Web), 12/09/2017, EFE

The development of a new efficient technology that allows high-speed wireless connections - with a transmission coverage of 100 Gbps per squared kilometer - applicable to the future 5G network is the objective of an european project participated by UPV.

Link to the news:

<http://www.lavanguardia.com/local/valencia/20170912/431221365945/proyecto-europeo-de-la-upv-busca-conexiones-inalambricas-de-alta-eficiencia.html>

- **Uusiteknologia Magazine** (<https://www.uusiteknologia.fi>)

Wireless data transmission at frequencies above 100 gigahertz

Uusiteknologia (Web), 21/09/2017, Unattributed

The European Union's Horizon 2020 Ultrawave project aims to develop technologies that are able to utilize the full spectrum of millimeter waves in the over 100 GHz band. A \$ 2.9 million project is being drawn by Lancaster University of England.

Link to the news: <https://www.uusiteknologia.fi/2017/09/21/langatonta-tiedonsiirtoa-yli-100-gigahertsin-taajuuksilla/>

From the information provided by the communication department and the web traffic statistics, we can conclude that the press releases have reached a wide audience, **resulting in more than 300.000 visits during the first month of the project**

4. ANNEX I: PRESS RELEASE

Engineers to pioneer unprecedented high speed wireless data coverage

A major new international research programme is responding to the overwhelming demand of internet traffic to develop ubiquitous wireless data coverage with unprecedented speed at millimetre waves.

For the first time in the Internet's history, the data used by tablets and smartphones now exceeds that of desktops. Emerging technologies and entertainment such as telemedicine, Internet of Things (IoT), 4K video streaming, cloud gaming, social networks, driverless cars, augmented reality and many other unpredictable applications will need zettabyte (1,000 billions of billions) of wireless data.

Smartphones will continue to work at microwave frequencies for many years because of microwaves' ability to pass through barriers. Though due to limitations to the amount of data that can be transmitted by microwaves, the only way to provide data with very fast download speeds is through covering urban areas with dense grids of micro, nano and pico 'cells', at microwave frequencies to serve a small number of users per cell.

However, manufacturers and operators have not yet solved how to feed a huge amount of data to a new maze of cells. Fibre is too expensive and difficult, if not impossible, to deploy in many urban areas, due city council permits or disruption.

A desirable solution is a wireless layer that can provide data at the level of tens of gigabit per second per kilometre square. It also needs to be flexible and come at a low cost.

Only the millimetre wave frequencies, 30–300 GHz, with their multi GHz bandwidths, could support tens of gigabit per second of wireless data rate. Unfortunately, rain can weaken or block data transmission and other technological limits have so far prevented the full exploitation of this portion of the spectrum.

The €2.9million European Union's Horizon 2020 ULTRAWAVE project, led by engineers at Lancaster University, aims, for the first time, to build technologies able to exploit the whole millimetre wave spectrum beyond 100 GHz.

The ULTRAWAVE concept is to create an ultra-capacity layer, aiming to achieve the 100 gigabit of data per second threshold, which is also flexible and easy to deploy. This layer will be able to feed data to hundreds of small and pico cells, regardless of the density of mobile devices in each cell. This would open scenarios for new network paradigms and architectures towards fully implementing 5G.

The ULTRAWAVE ultra capacity layer requires significant transmission power to cover wide areas overcoming the high attenuation at millimetre waves. This will be achieved by the convergence of three main technologies, vacuum electronics, solid-state electronics and photonics, in a unique wireless system, enabled by transmission power at multi Watt level. These power levels can only be generated through novel millimetre wave traveling wave tubes.

Professor Claudio Paoloni, Head of Engineering Department at Lancaster University and Coordinator of ULTRAWAVE, said: "When speeds of wireless networks equal fibre, billions of new rapid connections will help 5G become a reality. It is exciting to think that the EU Horizon 2020 ULTRAWAVE project could be a major milestone towards solving one of the main obstacles to future 5G networks, which is the ubiquitous wireless distribution of fibre-level high data rates.

"The huge growth in mobile devices and wireless data usage is putting an incredible strain on our existing wireless communication networks. Imagine crowded areas, such as London's Oxford Street, with tens of thousands of smartphone users per kilometre that wish to create, and receive content, with unlimited speed. To meet this demand, ULTRAWAVE will create European state of the art technologies for the new generation of wireless networks."

The ULTRAWAVE consortium includes five top Academic institutions and three high technology SMEs in millimetre wave and wireless technology, from five European countries: Lancaster

University in UK, Fibernova and Universitat Politecnica de Valencia in Spain, Ferdinand Braun Institute, Goethe University of Frankfurt and HF Systems GmbH & Co. KG in Germany, OMMIC in France and University of Rome Tor Vergata in Italy.

The ULTRAWAVE project is started on the 1st September 2017 and will be presented to the public by the Kickoff Workshop at Lancaster University on the 14th September 2017.

More information is available by visiting www.ultrawave2020.eu

5. ANNEX II: PRESS RELEASE (Spanish)

La UPV participa en un proyecto europeo para conseguir conexiones inalámbricas de alta velocidad y eficiencia en la futura 5G

- El proyecto ULTRAWAVE desarrollará una novedosa tecnología que permitirá transmisiones de 100 gigabits/s por kilómetro cuadrado
- En el proyecto participa el Centro de Tecnología Nanofotónica de la UPV

Desarrollar una nueva tecnología de bajo coste que permita conexiones inalámbricas a Internet de alta velocidad –con una cobertura de transmisión de 100 gigabits/s por kilómetro cuadrado- aplicable a la infraestructura de redes móviles de futura generación como la 5G. Este es el principal objetivo del proyecto europeo ULTRAWAVE, entre cuyos socios se encuentra la Universitat Politècnica de València, a través de su Centro de Tecnología Nanofotónica. Financiado por el programa Horizon 2020 de la UE, el proyecto está liderado por la Universidad de Lancaster.

A día de hoy, los datos utilizados por tabletas y teléfonos inteligentes superan ya a los requeridos por los ordenadores personales. Y en un futuro no muy lejano aplicaciones y servicios como el coche sin conductor, la telemedicina, el Internet de las Cosas (IoT), la transmisión de vídeo 4K, la realidad aumentada o los juegos en la nube necesitarán coberturas a nivel de zettabyte (1.000 billones de bytes) de datos inalámbricos.

Según explica José R. Ruiz, investigador del Centro de Tecnología Nanofotónica de la UPV, debido a las limitaciones de la cantidad de datos que se pueden transmitir por radio-comunicación, la única manera de ofrecerlos con velocidades de descarga muy rápidas para un teléfono inteligente es cubriendo áreas urbanas con densas redes de comunicaciones móviles, compuestas de micro, nano y pico celdas -más celdas para cursar el enorme tráfico de datos. “Sin embargo, los fabricantes y los operadores todavía no han solucionado eficientemente esa distribución de cantidades enormes de datos a un conjunto de nuevas celdas de una red móvil como 5G, ya que la fibra óptica es demasiado cara, difícil de desplegar, e inexistente en muchas áreas, especialmente las suburbanas y rurales”, añade José R. Ruiz.

Para paliar este déficit, los socios de ULTRAWAVE han ideado una nueva solución –una capa de ultra capacidad- que podrá proporcionar de forma inalámbrica datos al nivel de 100 gigabits por segundo por kilómetro cuadrado. La capa integra electrónica de vacío, electrónica en estado sólido y fotónica, en un sistema de radio-comunicación único.

“Sólo las frecuencias de onda milimétrica -espectro 30-300 GHz- con sus anchos de banda de multiGHz, podrían soportar decenas de gigabits por segundo de velocidad de datos inalámbricos. Ahora bien, este espectro no ha podido ser plenamente explotado hasta la fecha, debido a diferentes limitaciones; por ejemplo, la lluvia puede debilitar o bloquear la transmisión de los datos. El proyecto ULTRAWAVE tiene como objetivo, por primera vez, construir tecnologías capaces de explotar todo el espectro de ondas milimétricas más allá de los 100 GHz y de forma eficiente; tecnologías como los amplificadores de onda progresiva (TWT a 300 GHz) para lograr el enlace de transmisión, explica José R. Ruiz.

El Centro de Tecnología Nanofotónica de la UPV se encargará del diseño, desarrollo e implementación de la tecnología fotónica. Además, albergará las primeras pruebas de campo del proyecto, con la puesta en

marcha de una infraestructura piloto de red de comunicaciones móviles basadas en el uso de la nueva capa de ultracapacidad.

La solución ideada por los socios del proyecto permitiría ofrecer servicios de alta calidad y rapidez independientemente de la densidad de móviles que se acumulen en una zona determinada, favoreciendo además la implementación completa de la red 5G.

“Imaginemos áreas llenas de gente, como la Oxford Street de Londres, con decenas de miles de usuarios de smartphones por kilómetro que desean enviar y recibir contenido, con una velocidad ilimitada. ULTRAWAVE satisfará esta demanda, creando tecnologías europeas de vanguardia para la nueva generación de redes inalámbricas”, apunta Claudio Paoloni, jefe del Departamento de Ingeniería de la Universidad de Lancaster y coordinador de ULTRAWAVE.

Junto a la Universitat Politècnica de València y la Universidad de Lancaster, en el proyecto participan también la empresa valenciana Fibernova, el Instituto Ferdinand Braun, la Universidad Goethe de Frankfurt y HFSE (Alemania), OMMIC (Francia) y la Universidad de Roma Tor Vergata (Italia).

El proyecto ULTRAWAVE arrancó el pasado 1 de septiembre y se extenderá hasta agosto de 2020.

6. ANNEX III: EXAMPLES OF PRESS RELEASE PUBLICATIONS

UK team leads European effort to pioneer high speed wireless data coverage

By **Helen Knight** 19th September 2017 4:53 pm

Ubiquitous 5G wireless data coverage with speeds of up to 100 gigabits per second could be made possible by a European project developing technologies to exploit the millimetre wave spectrum.

The amount of data used by wireless devices such as tablets and smart phones already exceeds that of desktop computers, and is set to increase further as emerging technologies such as 4k video streaming, cloud gaming and augmented reality take off.

Increasing the amount of wireless data available will mean covering urban areas with dense grids of micro, nano and pico cells, each serving a small number of users.

But transmitting the data to these cells before it can be shared amongst users will be no easy task. Existing base stations are fed data through fibres, according to Professor Claudio Paoloni at Lancaster University. "But if the number of cells were to increase substantially, the fibre would be very difficult and expensive to install," he said.

One option is to use millimetre wave frequencies, in the 30-300GHz range, to transmit data wirelessly.

However, millimetre wave signals are susceptible to attenuation, or weakening, by rain and fog, said Paoloni, who is leading a €2.9million European Union Horizon 2020 project aiming to develop technologies to exploit this part of the spectrum.

The project, known as **ULTRAWAVE**, will develop a system with sufficient transmission

Link: <https://www.theengineer.co.uk/pioneer-high-speed-wireless-data-coverage/>

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The ULTRAWAVE programme will develop ubiquitous wireless data coverage with unprecedented speed at millimetre waves

A major new international research programme is responding to the overwhelming demand of internet traffic to develop ubiquitous wireless data coverage with unprecedented speed at millimetre waves.

For the first time in the Internet's history, the data used by tablets and smartphones now exceeds that of desktops. Emerging technologies and entertainment such as telemedicine, Internet of Things (IoT), 4K video streaming, cloud gaming, social networks, driverless cars, augmented reality and many other unpredictable applications will need zettabyte (1,000 billions of billions) of wireless data.

Smartphones will continue to work at microwave frequencies for many years

Link:

https://www.myscience.org.uk/wire/engineers_to_pioneer_unprecedented_high_speed_wireless_data_coverage-2017-lancaster

Engineers to pioneer unprecedented high speed wireless data coverage

Posted September 7, 2017

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Smartphones will continue to work at microwave frequencies for many years because of microwaves' ability to pass through barriers. Though due to limitations to the amount of data that can be transmitted by microwaves, the only way to provide data with very fast download speeds is through covering urban areas with dense grids of micro, nano and pico 'cells', at microwave frequencies to serve a small number of users per cell.

However, manufacturers and operators have not yet solved how to feed a huge amount of data to a new maze of cells. Fibre is too expensive and difficult, if not impossible, to deploy in many urban areas, due city council permits or disruption.

Link:

<https://www.technology.org/2017/09/07/engineers-to-pioneer-unprecedented-high-speed-wireless-data-coverage/>

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EU project to exploit mmWaves beyond 100GHz

27 September 2017

According to the recently launched Ultrawave project, only millimetre wave frequencies will be able to support data rates in excess of tens of Gbit/s needed in the future by 5G networks. But it says technological limits have, so far, prevented the full exploitation of this portion of the spectrum.

The €2.9million EU project, led by engineers at Lancaster University, is looking to build technologies that can exploit the millimetre wave spectrum beyond 100GHz.

Ultrawave plans to create what it calls an ultra-capacity layer. Not only will this attain data rates of 100Gbit/s, but will also be flexible and easy to deploy. The ultra capacity layer will then feed hundreds of small and pico cells.

Professor Claudio Paoloni, head of Lancaster's Engineering Department, said: "It is exciting to think that the Ultrawave project could be a major milestone towards solving one of the main obstacles to future 5G networks, which is the ubiquitous wireless distribution of fibre-level high data rates."

The ultra capacity layer will require 'significant transmission power', according to the project and this will be provided by vacuum electronics, solid-state electronics and photonics, with the necessary power levels generated through novel millimetre wave travelling wave tubes.

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A major new international research programme is responding to the overwhelming demand of internet traffic to develop ubiquitous wireless data coverage with unprecedented speed at millimetre waves.

For the first time in the Internet's history, the data used by tablets and smartphones now exceeds that of desktops. Emerging technologies and entertainment such as telemedicine, Internet of Things (IoT), 4K video streaming, cloud gaming, social networks, driverless cars, augmented reality and many other unpredictable applications will need zettabyte (1,000 billions of billions) of wireless data.

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Engineers to pioneer unprecedented high speed wireless data coverage

September 27, 2017

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A major new international research programme is responding to the overwhelming demand of internet traffic to develop ubiquitous wireless data coverage with unprecedented speed at millimetre waves.

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AIEMMAT UUTISET

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Pitkän kantaman takaisinsirontaa

Langaton runkoverkko millimetriaalloilla

21.09.2017

Lancasterin yliopiston insinöörien johtama 2,9 miljoonan euron Euroopan unionin Horizon 2020 Ultrawave -hankkeen tavoitteena on rakentaa ensimmäistä kertaa tekniikoita, jotka pystyvät hyödyntämään koko millimetriaaltojen spektriä yli 100 GHz:n taajuusalueella.

Ultrawave -konseptissa on tarkoitus luoda ultrakapasiteettinen verkkokerros, joka pyrkii saavuttamaan 100 gigabittiä dataa sekunnissa tason. Tällainen kerros pystyy syöttämään dataa satoihin pien- ja pikosoluihin riippumatta mobiililaitteiden tiheydestä soluissa, joten se avaa tietä uusille verkkoarkkitehtuureille, jotka tähtäävät täyden 5G:n toteuttamiseen.

Kehitettävä runkoverkkokerros tarjoaa yli 100 Gbps per neliökilometrin alalle Point to Multipoint tavalla D-kaistalla (141 - 174,8 GHz) yli 500 metrisen säteen kattavuudella ja sitä syöttää uudenlaiset G-kaistan (300 GHz) 600 metriset point-to-point linkit.

Vain millimetriaaltojen taajuuudet 30 - 300 GHz ja niiden usean GHz:n kaistanleveydet voivat tukea langatonta tiedonsiirtonopeutta kymmeniä gigabittejä sekunnissa. Valitettavasti sade voi heikentää tai estää tiedonsiirtoa ja muutkin tekniset rajat ovat toistaiseksi estäneet tämän taajuusalueen täyden hyödyntämisen.

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Julkaistu: 21.09.2017

Verkot

Lancasterin yliopiston insinöörien johtama 2,9 miljoonan euron Euroopan unionin Horizon 2020 Ultrawave -hankkeen tavoitteena on rakentaa ensimmäistä kertaa tekniikoita, jotka pystyvät hyödyntämään koko millimetriaaltojen spektriä yli 100 gigahertsin taajuusalueella.

Ultrawave -konseptissa on tarkoitus luoda ultrakapasiteettinen verkkokerros, joka pyrkii saavuttamaan 100 gigabittia dataa sekunnissa tason. Tällainen kerros pystyy

Tilaa uutiskirje!

Kolumni

Tämä on seuraava askel piiriteknikassa: eFPGA

On selvää, että puolijohdealalla kaskitytään vihdoin kasvavaan valikoimaan teknologioita, jotka prosessigeometrian kutistamisen sijaan katsovat uusia järjestelmäarkkitehtuureita ja käytettävissä olevan piiri- ja laite- ja koteloitusuunnittelun konseptien kautta. Kun astumme uudelle aikakaudelle, seuraava looginen askel näyttää olevan FPGA-piirin ja prosessorin eli CPU:n yhdistäminen: sulautettu FPGA.

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http://www.horizon2020projects.com/pr-knowledge-innovation/engineers-pioneer-high-speed-wireless-data/

The screenshot shows the Horizon 2020 Projects website. At the top left, the logo features three stars and the text 'HORIZON 2020 PROJECTS' with contact information for UK and Brussels offices. A navigation bar includes links for 'EU Commissioners', 'Special Reports', 'Partners', 'HorizonTV', 'Publications', 'Testimonials', and 'About us', along with a search box and social media icons. A sidebar on the left lists 'HORIZON 2020 PILLARS' such as 'EXCELLENT SCIENCE', 'INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP', 'SOCIETAL CHALLENGES', 'POLICY & RESEARCH', and 'GLOBAL COLLABORATION', plus a 'Subscribe' button. The main content area displays a news article under the heading 'H2020: INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP: ICT'. The article features a large image of hands holding various mobile devices displaying augmented reality content. The article title is 'Engineers pioneer high-speed wireless data', dated 29 September 2017, by Oyundari Zorigtbaatar. The text describes an international research programme responding to the demand for high-speed wireless data for emerging technologies like telemedicine and IoT. To the right, there are three smaller article teasers: 'Sharing Cities launch London clear a r programme' (27/09/17), 'Guardian Angel: improving the lives of dementia patients' (21/09/17), and a partially visible one at the bottom.

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1 Technology

Engineers To Pioneer Unprecedented High Speed Wireless Data Coverage

September 29, 2017 Eurasia Review 0 Comment Computers, Engineering, Internet, Smartphones

By Eurasia Review

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A major new international research programme is responding to the overwhelming demand of internet traffic to develop ubiquitous wireless data coverage with unprecedented speed at millimetre waves.

For the first time in the Internet's history, the data used by tablets and smartphones now exceeds that of desktops. Emerging technologies and entertainment such as telemedicine, Internet of Things (IoT), 4K video streaming, cloud gaming, social networks, driverless cars,

augmented reality and many other unpredictable applications will need zettabyte (1,000 billions of billions) of wireless data.

Smartphones will continue to work at microwave frequencies for many years because of microwaves' ability to pass through barriers. Though due to limitations to the amount of data that can be transmitted by microwaves, the only way to provide data with very fast download speeds is through covering urban areas with dense grids of micro, nano and pico 'cells', at microwave frequencies to serve a small number of users per cell.

The screenshot shows the AlphaGalileo website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with categories like 'All regions', 'Africa', 'Asia', 'Caribbean', 'Europe', 'Latin America', 'Middle East', 'North America', 'Oceania', and 'Extraterrestrial'. Below this is a secondary navigation bar with 'All categories' and sub-categories like 'Science', 'Health', 'Society', 'Humanities', 'Arts', 'Applied science', and 'Business'. The main content area features a 'News Release' section with a Lancaster University logo and the headline 'Engineers to pioneer unprecedented high speed wireless data coverage'. The article text discusses a major international research programme responding to the demand for high-speed wireless data coverage. To the right of the article is a search box with fields for 'Keywords', 'All Regions', 'All Categories', and 'All Content', along with a 'Search' button. Below the search box are sections for 'Other content in...' with sub-sections for 'Categories', 'Keywords', and 'Regions'. At the bottom right, there are logos for 'expertsvr.' and 'The OPEN Notebook'.

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Engineers to pioneer unprecedented high speed wireless data coverage
26 September 2017 Lancaster University
A major new international research programme is responding to the overwhelming demand of internet traffic to develop ubiquitous wireless data coverage with unprecedented speed at millimetre waves.
For the first time in the Internet's history, the data used by tablets and smartphones now exceeds that of desktops. Emerging technologies and entertainment such as telemedicine, Internet of Things (IoT), 4K video streaming, cloud gaming, social networks, driverless cars, augmented reality and many other unpredictable applications will need zettabyte (1,000 billions of billions) of wireless data.
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However, manufacturers and operators have not yet solved how to feed a huge amount of data to a new maze of cells. Fibre is too expensive and difficult, if not impossible, to deploy in many urban areas, due city council permits or disruption.

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Breaking science news on the move from AlphaGalileo.